

CHALLENGES AND IMPACTS OF SINGLE PARENTING ON STUDENTS' LEARNING IN GOVERNMENT SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN IRINGA MUNICIPALITY, TANZANIA

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Abstract: This study aimed to investigate the impacts and challenges of single parenting on students' learning in government secondary schools in Iringa Municipality, Tanzania. The study used mixed methods (qualitative and quantitative research methods). Study population included 30 secondary school students and 15 parents; to make the sample size of 45 respondents. Purposive sampling technique was used in this study. Instrument used for data collection was questionnaires and semi-structured interview. Data were analysed by using qualitative content analysis and quantitative data were analysed by using descriptive statistics to generate frequency and percentages by applying data checking, editing, coding, reliability and analysis. Spss version 22 was used. Also, trustworthiness was used to ensure data correctness by measuring its credibility, transferability, and dependability. Ethics considered informed consent, confidentiality, non-maleficence, and plagiarism. Key findings: Low academic performance, lack of time to control and guide their children, Lack of economic support, insufficient social support, lack of parental attention and nurturing, Inability to buy school requirements, lack of opportunity to check their children progress, poor communication basing on academic matters, leads to psychological problems like life stress, instability, anxiety and depression. The study concluded that, all single parents are likely to be caused by divorce, separation, death and unmarried which hinders students' academic performance in secondary schools. Recommended, all single parent should prepare requirements for their children and discuss with them concerning academic matters. Headmistresses/headteachers should provide necessary support including counselling to encourage them in their studies. Government support also necessary to single parent students.

Keywords: Effect, Single parenting, students 'learning; government secondary schools.

1. INTRODUCTION

The study aimed to investigate challenges and impacts of single parenting on students' learning in government secondary schools in Iringa municipality, Tanzania. It is well known that family plays a crucial role in society, being the initial socializing agent for a child and exerting a significant influence on the child's physical, mental, moral, and social development (Roska & Potter, 2016). Its primary responsibility is to instill societal norms and values in the child (Roska & Potter, 2016). The foundation of a person's societal identity is established in the home during early life (Davis, 2017). Agulana (1999) emphasizes that the family sets the psychological, moral, and spiritual foundations for a child's overall development. A child's educational path is often determined by the family's background, whether affluent or impoverished, educated or not (Salami & Alawode, 2000).

Parents bear the primary responsibility for their children's educational and career development (Salami & Alawode, 2000). When parents fail in their duty to guide their children through life's stages, it can adversely affect the children's academic performance (Salami & Alawode, 2000). However, circumstances such as divorce, denied paternity, separation, and death of a spouse sometimes necessitate single-parenting (Nyakutse, 2016; Thwala, 2018). Various challenges like divorce, poverty, urban migration, and health pandemics contribute to the breakdown of family structures, affecting children's development (Thwala, 2018).

Single parenting is wide spread globally which leads to the involvement of one parent taking the responsibilities of upbringing due to divorce, separation, having children outside of marriage, or the death of a spouse (Henshin, 2015; Salami & Alawode, 2018). Children in single-parent households may face deprivation, denial of rights, and increased exposure to anti-social behaviors and poor academic performance (Amato, 2016). Studies consistently demonstrate the impact of single-parent families on a child's educational achievement, revealing that children raised in single-parent households are at risk of not reaching their full potential academically (Zill, 2016). The absence of one parent can create a gap in the child's support system, affecting their academic performance (Nyarko, 2017).

Single-parent households in Sub-Saharan African Countries and all over the world are often associated with higher poverty rates compared to two-parent intact households, leading to socioeconomic disadvantages and potential emotional and behavioral disorders in children (Lee, et.al, 2017). The family structure has a direct correlation with a child's academic performance, with nuclear intact families generally yielding better academic outcomes (Zill, 2016). Students from step-parent families tend to perform better than those from single-parent households (Sander, 2017). Challenges unique to single-parents, such as bitterness towards the absent spouse, loneliness, poverty, and insecurity, further contribute to the negative impact on academic performance (Amoakohene, 2019).

In Tanzania, a significant portion of children live in single-parent households, facing multiple challenges that hinder their educational progress (Mrinde, 2014; Tahir, 2021). Factors like low income, teachers' attitudes towards parents, parents' level of education, and poor communication between teachers and parents impede parental involvement and subsequently affect students' academic performance (Bashag, 2020). In Iringa Municipality, the prevalence of single-parent households is notable, and children from such backgrounds tend to exhibit traits of lower assertiveness and increased aggression and submission in schools, resulting in subpar learning outcomes (MoEST, 2020). The influence of single parenting on students' learning in secondary schools in Tanzania, particularly in Iringa Municipality, warrants further investigation (Frieman, 2021).

Up to now, Iringa Region is among the leading regions with children living with single parents out of having a campaign of stopping early pregnancy and marriage to the people still the rate of single parent families is high (Mtweve, 2012). Besides this, there have been mass campaigns and education through various mass media on impact of being single parent in rising children in the society but does not change their behaviour due to ignorance, poverty and denial.

Existing studies have largely overlooked the role of single parenting as a factor affecting students' education (Donkor, 2018; Farooq, *et al.*, 2019; Mahama and Campion, 2021). Instead, they have primarily focused on variables such as socioeconomic status, parental education, student attitudes, school environment, housing, and residential experiences. Recent evidence suggests a decline in the quality of education among students from certain family structures, particularly those raised in fatherless households (Malumbo, 2019). The absence of one adult in the family, as commonly observed in single-parent households, has been attributed as a key explanation for the challenges faced by children in such families (Frieman, 2021). These challenges extend beyond childhood, affecting the children's physical, mental, social, and psychological well-being, including access to healthcare (Clark & Hamplova, 2018).

However, achieving academic success is not solely dependent on students' efforts, as other factors also play a role. With the changing family structures worldwide, single-parent households have become more prevalent, contrasting the traditional nuclear family (Kaimen, 2019). Regardless of whether the single-parent households are headed by mothers or fathers, children in these families tend to underperform compared to their peers from two-parent households (Lee, 2017). Multiple stressors, such as economic disadvantage, psychological trauma, behavioural issues, and physical ailments, contribute to the decline in academic performance among students residing in single-parent households (Fontenot *et al.*, 2018). Consequently, this study aimed to investigate the influence of single parenting on students' learning in secondary schools within Iringa Municipality.

The government is responsible for ensuring there is access to quality education to all citizens. The study increased efforts on policy formulation concerning access to quality education especially to students with single parents. The study informed and guided policy makers on obstacles that hindered single parents especially on child's education so as to formulate policies in accordance to the foreseen obstacles which may guide learning institutions on how to handle students from single parented families. Moreover, the study findings helped to provide the ways forward that helped the government and the concerned community to arrive at the desired targets of education to all. The study benefited and helped the academicians as their guide and also acted as a bridge to some gaps that the previous researchers left concerning the influence of single parenting on students learning in secondary schools. The study also added knowledge to the existing knowledge on influence of single parenting on students learning in secondary schools. Moreover, the study provided other researchers with areas for future research on related topic areas.

This study provided the direct feedback to single parents from being aware on how single parented life affects students learning. This paved a way on influencing parents to take their responsibilities fully on supporting their children to school learning. Single parents learned both positive and negative effects of single parenting for the purpose of improving students learning in secondary schools. Also, the study pin pointed the influence of single parents that should play in boosting students learning in secondary schools, it added and provided new knowledge to the single parents on how to deal with students learning in secondary schools.

This study was very useful in the real world as it was a foundation for future researchers carrying out their studies on the influence of single parenting on students learning in secondary schools and other related fields. Other researchers would use this study to conduct studies in the recommended areas for further studies and use it as a source of reference. In addition, the study was chosen to be conducted because it provided skilful parenting practices and resulted to be critical in buffering youngsters' families, such as children grow up knowing how to value life, take good care, respect rules and regulations and be given enough protection and preventive health education.

This study was conducted in Iringa Municipality, specifically at Nduli, Kihesa and Mtwivila government secondary schools. These schools were selected based on easy accessibility of information and area familiarity. In recent years, the quality of education was falling among the students from certain family structures. Therefore, the study aimed to explore the influence of single parenting on students learning in government secondary schools in Tanzania, taking Iringa Municipality as the case of study. There was a rapid increase in the number of single-parent families in the latter half of the twentieth century. This change has been used by some people to argue that we are witnessing a breakdown of the family, with negative effects on children, families and society (Popenoe, 2016). Others suggest that single-parent families have been present in all societies over time and should not be viewed as abnormal or problematic but rather as an alternative family form. (Coontz, 2017). No matter what people view about the presence of single parent families yet the presence of families headed by one-parent has a major influence on the social, economic and political context of family life as far as education of the children is concern. Due to the fact that single parented children face many challenges throughout their development.

The challenges and on their education are raised and discussed as follow: -

Most of single-parent families have a low level of economic power and therefore they cannot provide their children with school requirements like school fees, text books, exercise books and other learning materials. Though some of single parent are rich yet many are poor. Family poverty also can lead to other problems such as diseases, poor school attendance and performance and psychological problems. Pong and Ju (2020) comment that for many low-income or single-parent families, the challenges that are mostly faced by children and youths are directly or indirectly related to the poor economic condition for their families, not just to parenting style. Poverty directly reduces the access and quality of resources, social and health services and opportunities such as food, shelter, health care, education, and transportation. Fraser (2018) also maintains that poverty affects the ability of parents to provide consistent supervision and monitoring, adequate family management practices, and a range of social and educational stimulating experiences. Due to less income single parent children suffer much in getting education resources which make some of them to be the victims of child labour hence they can be dropouts or have poor performance and fail to achieve their dreams.

Tehan (2017) argued single parent students are a special population who require different avenues of advisement than traditional students due to unique responsibilities and role strain. Stressors which would present ordinary challenges to traditional college students can present extraordinary difficulty for single parents who must schedule child care, care for sick children, and prioritize work/financial support with allocation of time for study in order to ensure academic success (Freeman, 2015).

Impact of single parenting are narrated by various researchers as follows:

Lack of access to higher education results in lack of hiring in fully benefited positions. Lack of benefits and absent degrees results in lack of adequate healthcare coverage, lack of retirement, and lower pay. Lower pay results in inability to pay for adequate childcare, resulting in children with lower academic outcomes, increased incidence of illnesses and accidents, and higher rates of truancy. Healthcare and education inadequacies debilitate a women's ability to earn an adequate income (Horrell, 2017; Gornick, Munzi, Sierminska, & Smeeding, 2019). Lone motherhood and interrelated facets of social bias women face when attempting to obtain formal employment act to perpetuate and exacerbate existing risk for female poverty (Ms. Foundation for Women, 2018; Babcock & Laschever, 2015; Shartzter, Long, & Benet, healthcare, and housing (Allard & Sheldon, 2015; Jones-DeWeever & Gault, 2018).

According to Salami & Alawode (2018), single parenting is a result of divorce, different types of separation, having children out of wedlock, or the passing of one spouse, which leaves the tasks in the hands of the single parent. Because the single parent may be overburdened with duties in such a family structure, the children may not receive the attention they deserve. Children in single-parent households are more likely to experience deprivation and to be denied access to certain chances and rights, according to Amato (2019). They are more likely to engage in antisocial behaviour and have subpar academic performance.

Mkubwa (2020), a research on the impact of single motherhood on academic achievement in Rungwe District, contrasts this with some Tanzanian literature that has focused heavily on the general obstacles faced by students from single parent families. The study found that students from single-parent families performed worse academically than their peers from intact families. These students had to rely on one parent for support, and sometimes they had to engage in economic activities to support themselves and the family, which took away from time that should have been spent studying and negatively impacted their performance in school.

Also, Usakli (2020) conducted a research study on the effects of single-parent households on student academic behaviour, success, attendance and suspensions in Tanzania and found that children with single parents are missing direct relationship with their parents which lead them to be less assertive and more aggressive and submissive in schools which lead to poor academic performance than children with two parents. By evaluating the impact of single mothers' parenting on students' learning in secondary school, specifically in the Iringa municipality, this study aimed to fill this information vacuum.

Globally, family income has taken on a determining role in education. Kadushinn (2017) suggested that children's academic performance and educational success are both hampered by low income. This is particularly apparent in households with only one parent, where one parent is responsible for meeting the children's emotional, social, and financial requirements. A single parent may thus run the danger of growing distant from their children and jeopardizing their capacity to perform in school due to the stress of having to provide for the family's basic needs, such as food, shelter, and clothing.

Jensen (2018) discovered that certain kids from low-income parents have trouble understanding and don't even learn as quickly as other kids. Because their parents do not have the time to help them at home, their vocabulary may be less and less developed than that of other children from families with higher incomes, as well as their methods of understanding. This frequently occurs in households with single parents who take on the responsibilities of both parents and may not have enough time to monitor their children's academic progress. This is made worse by the fact that the single parent will have to work all day and will have little to no time to assist the kids with their schoolwork. Due to the lack of assistance and occasionally even concern for their academic progress, these may have an impact on their grades. A strong financial incentive for education is a crucial motivator for kids to do well.

According to Kashen (2015), students with educated parents perform better in academic tasks. According to Dale and Griffith (2018), a parent's education affects a child's performance, and where a single parent is educated, the impact is felt by the children as well, though not as strongly as if both parents were present and educating them at the same time. Similar findings were made by Douglas (2018), who stressed the value of a mother's education due to the fact that she has far more interaction with her kid than the father and that this has a significant impact.

Obe (2017) claims that educated parents can support their children's motivation to learn by giving them rewards in addition to just encouraging them to learn. Higher levels of education, for instance, may make it easier for parents to get involved in their kids' education. They may also make it possible for parents to learn and practice social skills and problem-solving

techniques that will help their kids succeed in school. This might not be the case for single parents, who might not have the time to mentor and actively participate in their children's education due to a lack of time. Students' ability to study will be boosted if their parents have better levels of education and are interested in their education.

Previous studies worldwide on single parenting on students learning have been done on different areas of interest. Many researchers have conducted studies in different areas of choice concerning how single parenting may affect students learning from such background, performance, behaviour, wellbeing among them. Some studies focused on primary school pupils, while others focused on private secondary schools.

For instance, Salami (2000) studied the influence of Single parenting on academic achievement of adolescents in secondary schools: implication for counselling in Nigeria. Wanjiku (2010) did a research on impact of family conflicts on the academic performance and interpersonal relationship of pupils in public primary schools, Azuka-Obiek (2013) did a study on single parenting, psychological well-being and academic performance of adolescents in Nigeria, Mrinde (2014) did a research on single parents and children in her study she investigated the challenges that single parented students face in attaining primary school education in Kinondoni, Malima (2016) did a research on effects of single parenting on the student's academic performance in secondary schools in Arusha, Samwel (2018) investigated the influence of pupils academic performance in primary schools in Arusha, Manengelo (2020) did research on effects of single parenting on the student's academic performance in secondary schools in Kinondoni, Shitindi (2022) investigated single mother-parenting on adolescent's development in Dodoma City, Ezeufondu (2022) investigate on the effects of broken families on students' academic achievement in private secondary schools in Iringa.

Therefore, this study aimed at finding out the influence of single parenting on students learning in government secondary schools in Iringa Municipality. Although other studies have explored on causes, effects of single parents and broken families but the environment where those studies conducted are different with Iringa municipality. This, study therefore, focus on challenges and impact of single parenting on students learning in government secondary schools. A phenomenological research design was used in the investigation. Phenomenological research is an approach to inquiry that focuses on participant reported descriptions of participants' lived experiences with a phenomenon. This summary captures the essence of the experiences for a number of people who have all encountered the phenomenon. Interviews are frequently conducted as part of this design, which has solid philosophical foundations (Creswell, 2018). The methodology was used in this study because it was effective at identifying subjective experiences, gaining understanding of people's motives and behaviours, and slicing through the clutter of widely held beliefs and presumptions.

This study was supported by the several theories basing on the challenges and impact of single parenting on students' learning in government secondary schools in Iringa municipality, Tanzania; includes:

Social Learning Theory

Social learning theory was influenced by the work of Albert Bandura in (1971) due to his curiosity on how the society or environmental factors can influence behaviour just by observing. Social learning theory combines cognitive learning theory (which posits that learning is influenced by psychological factors) and behavioural learning theory (which depicts that learning is based on responses to environmental stimuli). Albert Bandura integrated these two theories and came up with four requirements for learning: observation (environmental), retention (cognitive), reproduction (cognitive), and motivation.

This integrative approach to learning was called social learning theory. In addition to the observation of behaviour, learning also occurs through the observation of rewards and punishments, a process known as vicarious reinforcement. The theory expands on traditional behavioural theories, in which behaviour is governed solely by reinforcements, by placing emphasis on the important roles of various internal processes in the learning individual (Bandura, 1971).

In Social Learning theory Albert Bandura (1977) contented with the behaviourist learning theories of classical conditioning and operant conditioning. However, he adds two important notions: mediating processes occur between stimuli and responses and behaviour is learned from the environment through the process of observational learning. This is illustrated during the famous Bobo-doll experiment (Bandura, 1981). In Bandura's experiment three groups of children aged three; four and five years were exposed to a film of a model who was an adult. The adult was behaving aggressively towards a Bobo doll (an inflated plastic doll). After watching the adult model, the children were allowed to play with the doll themselves. Individuals that are observed are called models. Social learning theory suggests that the environment can have

an effect on the way people behave. Social learning theory was applicable to this study due to its category of learning theories which is grounded on the belief that human behaviour is determined by a three-way relationship between cognitive factors, environmental influences, and behaviour.

Attachment Theory

Attachment theory, developed by John Bowlby, focuses on the impact of early relationships on human development. In the context of single parenting and students' learning in secondary schools, attachment theory is relevant because it suggests that the quality of the parent-child relationship, even in the case of a single parent, can significantly influence a student's academic performance and socio-emotional development.

Behaviourism Theory

Behaviourism is primarily concerned with observable and measurable aspects of human behaviour. In defining behaviour, behaviourist learning theories emphasize changes in behaviour that result from stimulus-response associations made by the learner. John B. Watson (1878-1958) and B. F. Skinner (1904-1990) are the two principal originators of behaviourist approaches to learning. Watson believed that human behaviour resulted from specific stimuli that elicited certain responses. In assuming that human behaviour is learned, behaviourists also hold that all behaviours can also be unlearned, and replaced by new behaviours; that is, when behaviour becomes unacceptable, it can be replaced by an acceptable one. A key element this theory of learning is the rewarded response. The desired response must be rewarded in order for learning to take place (Parkay & Hass, 2000).

In education, advocates of behaviourism have effectively adopted this system of rewards and punishments in their classrooms by rewarding desired behaviours and punishing inappropriate ones. Rewards vary, but must be important to the learner in some way. For example, if a teacher wishes to teach the behaviour of remaining seated during the class period, the successful student's reward might be checking the teacher's mailbox, running an errand, or being allowed to go to the library to do homework at the end of the class period. As with all teaching methods, success depends on each student's stimulus and response, and on associations made by each learner. Using behaviourist theory in the classroom can be rewarding for both students and teachers. Behavioural change occurs for a reason; students work for things that bring them positive feelings, and for approval from people they admire. They change behaviours to satisfy the desires they have learned to value. They generally avoid behaviours they associate with unpleasantness and develop habitual behaviours from those that are repeated often (Parkay & Hass, 2000). The entire rationale of behaviour modification is that most behaviour is learned. If behaviours can be learned, then they can also be unlearned or relearned. A behaviour that goes unrewarded will be extinguished. Consistently ignoring an undesirable behaviour will go far toward eliminating it. When the teacher does not respond angrily, the problem is forced back to its source—the student. Other successful classroom strategies are contracts, consequences, punishment and others that have been described in detail earlier. Behaviourist learning theory is important in achieving desired behaviour in mainstream education. Special education teachers have classroom behaviour modification plans to implement for their students. These plans assure success for these students in and out of school.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of this research, the researcher used a mixed methods approach (quantitative and qualitative). This approach offered a promising means of advancing the study of single parenting on students learning in government secondary schools in Tanzania, Iringa Municipality. Integrating semi-structured interviews and qualitative analysis into a quantitative program of research on Single Parenting resulted in valuable scientific insight and generation of novel objectives for testing. This mixed methods approach is described and recommended for integrating qualitative data into quantitative research are provided. Quantitative approach was used for seeking structured responses while qualitative was used for ascertaining the views because students learning was subjective (Wick, 2020). The population of the study included 30 students from Single Parenting households from Nduli, Kihesa and Mtwivila secondary schools and 15 parents as key informants from Iringa Municipality. Selection of respondents was done through the purposive sampling technique. Sample size was 45 respondents.

The methods of data collection were through questionnaires and semi-structured interview. Validity refers to the extent to which the measurement instruments accurately measure what they were designed to measure by giving sufficient coverage

of the research topic (Pallant, 2013). The researcher used second-hand the most common type of construct validity which was the content validity (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2017). For content validity, the researcher submitted the questionnaires to the supervisor who is an expert in the field and also asked the practitioners on the content of validity before the distribution of the questionnaires to the respondents.

Nevertheless, the pilot study was the complement the content validity of the questionnaires prepared for data collections. As a result, various professionals in the field of psychology evaluated the components that made up a scale for each variable to see how well they were appropriate and what important modifications should be made to assure their validity.

Reliability of measurement was established by examining the stability and consistency of the data. Consistency indicates how well the items (variables) measuring a concept grouped together as a set. Subsequently, the result achieved was compared with the rules of thumb showed in Cronbach’s alpha that was interpreted the coefficient alpha values. In this study, the Cronbach’s alpha reliability coefficient expressed as a coefficient between 0 and 1 was used. The closer Cronbach’s alpha coefficient is to 1.0 the greater the internal consistency of the items in the scale. According to the rules of thumb, the value of reliability alpha of > 0.7 and composite & overall reliability > 0.60 is acceptable.

Data were analysed by using qualitative content analysis while quantitative data was analysed using descriptive statistics to generate frequency and percentages. The researcher adopted a number of steps that included data checking, data editing, data coding, data reliability and data analysis. SPSS software Version 22 was used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics analysis was used based on the data obtained through the questionnaire.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to explore challenges and impacts of single parenting on students learning in government secondary schools in Iringa Municipality Tanzania. The study was guided by the following research questions: -

- i. What are the challenges of single parenting on students’ learning in government secondary schools in Iringa Municipality, Tanzania?
- ii. What are the impacts of single parenting on students’ learning in government secondary school in Iringa Municipality, Tanzania?

Table 1: Represent results of research question 1.

S/N	ITEMS	AGREE	DISAGREE
1.	low level of economic power they lack ability to provide school requirements like school fees, text books, exercise books and other learning materials to their children	40 (88.8%)	5 (11.1%)
2.	Family poverty also can lead to other problems such as diseases, poor school attendance	38 (84.4%)	7 (15.5%)
3.	Inability to provide consistent supervision and monitoring to children in schools	42 (93.3%)	3 (6.6%)
4.	Lack of time to control and guide their children	35 (77.7%)	10 (22.2%)
5.	Lack of opportunity to check their children Progress	41 (91.1%)	4 (8.8%)
6.	Lack of opportunity to check their children Progress	43 (95.5%)	2 (4.4%)
7.	Poor communication basing on academic matters	39 (86.6%)	6 (13.3%)

The second research question was:

What are the impacts of single parenting on students’ learning in government secondary school in Iringa Municipality, Tanzania?

Table 2: Represent the results of research question 2

S/N	ITEM	AGREE	DISAGREE
1.	Low academic performance	42 (93.3%)	3 (6.6%)
2.	Students mental outcome	37 (82.2%)	8 (17.7%)
3.	Social, emotional outcome	40 (88.8%)	5 (11.1%)
4.	Lack of economic support for school use	38 (84.4%)	7 (15.5%)
5.	Insufficient social service support	41 (91.1%)	4 (8.8%)
6.	Lack of parental attention and nurturing	39 (86.6%)	6 (13.3%)
7.	Inability to buy school requirements	43 (95.5%)	2 (4.4%)
8.	Behavioral outcomes	35 (77.7%)	10 (22.2%)
9.	Some students become the victims of child Labour	40 (88.8%)	5 (11.1%)
10.	Poor communication basing on academic matters	36 (82.2%)	9 (20%)
11.	Leads to psychological problems like life stress, instability, anxiety and depression	44 (97.7%)	1 (2.2%)
12.	Lack of access to higher education	45 (100%)	0 (00%)

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions for research question 1

The study concluded that there are a number of challenges which arise as a result of single parenting on students’ learning in government secondary schools in Iringa Municipality, Tanzania; as it has been explained by the respondents in the process of data collection for the fulfilment of the study. Therefore, there is a great need of active involvement of both parents positively impacts children's academic performance, emphasizing the need for cooperation regardless of parental status. Emotional, financial issues, and time constraints can hinder academic success. Parental engagement, including monitoring school work, is vital for a child's educational progress. The research concluded that when both parents are available to their children, the children will do great in their studies. The children need cooperation from their parents whether they are raised by single parents or both for their success during study time.

Recommendations for research question 1

Recommendations include providing support to single parents through government and NGOs to enhance economic stability. Addressing cultural practices that hinder single mothers from supporting their children is crucial. Training on single mothers' rights and social welfare support is advised. Encouraging socialization through support groups and counseling programs for single parents is important. Introducing school guidance and counseling departments and fostering cooperation between schools and families can enhance students' educational success. Teachers should advise parents to supervise academic progress and balance domestic chores with studies.

Conclusion for research question 2

The impacts of single parenting on students’ learning in government secondary school in Iringa Municipality, affects a number of secondary school students in academic matters. It is true and well known that through the support from both parents is a key point for their children’s’ academic performance in schools, as they are preparing for their future life. It is important for parents to put in consideration on their children’s growth and training before they decide to divorce. Single parenting leads to emotional problem, financial problems and adjustments difficulties affect the academic performance of the students. Also, some parents have no time to be with their children due to their work, thereby not having time to check their school work. Therefore, parents are better to be live together for the purpose of providing care and support to their children especially for the issues of academic.

Recommendation on the research question 2

be in place to empower single parents with prerequisite tools that will help them become economically stable. Social cultural practices that stigmatize and deprive single women's property and consequently hinder single parents from supporting their children adolescents should be stopped. Social welfare officers should provide training to the community on the rights of single mothers to live, to be respected, to own land and other property and to be supported. The government and nongovernmental organizations should support single parents in forming groups for socialization and offering counselling programmers as intervention measures to their situations.

School system should introduce guidance and counselling department where learners who are facing problems at home or school to be able to share with the teacher and assist the learners where it is needed. When schools and families work cohesively to motivate, socialize, and educate students, students reach higher levels of educational triumph. Teachers should advise parents to co-operate with the school administrations so as to do supervision of their children academic progress and through balancing of domestic chores with studies at home. This will improve their studies. To gather more generalizable results, a future study suggestion might be to replicate this study in other geographical areas with a more diverse population. If the population exemplified more diversity in terms of demographics like race, household make up and socioeconomic status there may be a difference in the results of the study. Another future study suggestion could be beneficial to allow parent participants the opportunity to elaborate on questions that were asked on the parent survey. Providing further explanations to support initial responses i.e., why they are not able to regularly attend parent-teacher conferences, may provide deeper insight pertaining to the amount of parental involvement.

REFERENCES

- [1] Amato, P.R. (2019). *Life –span Adjustment of children to their Parents' divorce*. The future of children 4:143 –164.
- [2] Amoakohene, C. E. (2019). Children of divorce-coping with divorce: A randomized control trial of an online prevention program for youth experiencing parental divorce. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 83(5), 999–1005.
- [3] Bashag, H. (2020). Psychological Adjustment and Substance Use among Adolescents before and after a Parental Divorce. *Child Development Journal*, 62, 328–337.
- [4] Davis, K. E. (2017). *Review of Children of divorce: stories of loss and growth*. Columbia: Tyler and Francis.
- [5] Eamon, M. (2018). Social- demographic, school, neighborhood, and parenting influences on academic achievement of Latino young adolescents. *Journal of Youth and Adolescents*, 34(2),163-175.
- [6] Fadeye, J. D. (2019). *A text of social studies; socialization and political culture international organization for NCE- and Undergraduates*. Ibadan: Etori.
- [7] Frieman, H. (2021). Single Family Environments and Problematic Adolescents: Toward an Empirically Based Typology. *Child Development Journal*, 63(2), 51–74.
- [8] Henshin, J. (2015). *Contemporary educational psychology*. New York: Longman Publishers.
- [9] Hochschild, Jennifer, L. (2016). Social Class in Public Schools. *Journal of Social Issues*, 59 (4), 821-840.
- [10] Lee, D. (2017). Single mother statistics. Retrieved from: <https://singlemotherguide.com/singlemother-statistics>.
- [11] Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (MoEST). (2020). *Students' Performance based on Single Parents. A Survey Conducted to Enhance Performance of Students with Single Parents in Tanzania*. July, 2020. Dar es Salaam.
- [12] Mkubwa, A. (2020). *Influence of Single Parenthood on Academic Performance of Students in Secondary Schools: A study of Rungwe District in Mbeya Region, Tanzania*. Masters of Arts in Education. University of Dodoma.
- [13] Mrinde, R. (2014). Coping with Divorce: A Study of Young Adolescents Challenges that Single Parented Students Faces in Tanzania. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*. 10(2), 745–812.
- [14] Nyakutse, G. (2016). *Communicating to with Children in Crisis. Paper presented at the 8thnetwork conference for preschool teacher training and development in Southern Africa held April, 22nd – 28th in Manzini Swaziland*.

- [15] Nyarko, K. (2017). Parental Involvement: A Sine Qua Non in Adolescents' Educational Achievement. *Unpublished Doctor of Philosophy Thesis*, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität, München.
- [16] Pong, S. & Ju, D. B. (2020). The effects of change in family structure and income on dropping out of middle and high school. *Journal of Family Issues*, 21, 147–169.
- [17] Roska, J., & Potter, D. (2016). Parenting and academic achievement: Intergenerational transmission of educational advantage. *Journal of Sociology in Education*, 84: 299-318.
- [18] Salami, S., & Alawode, E. (2018). Influence of single parenting on the academic achievement of adolescents in secondary schools: Implications for counselling. *Ilorin Journal of Education*, 20: 1-8.
- [19] Sander, K. (2019). Influence of Family Status on Children's School Development in Kenya. *Canadian Journal of School Psychology*, 16(1), 39–52.
- [20] Thwala, S. (2018). *The psychosocial world of orphans and vulnerable children: The implications of psychosocial support for orphans and vulnerable children in Swaziland*. Germany: VDM Verlag.
- [21] Usakli, G. (2020). Effects of single-parent households on student academic behaviour, success, attendance and suspensions in Tanzania. *Journal of Youth and Adolescents*, 34(2), 163-175.
- [22] Uwaifo, V.O. (2018). *The effects of family structure and parenthood on the academic performance of Nigerian University students*.
- [23] Zill, C. (2016). Family Structure, Family Process, and Adolescent Well-Being. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 6(4), 457–488.